

**Families on the Margins:
Institutional Gaps and Care Burdens in Households
with Children Affected by Behavioral and Cognitive Disorders**

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Abstract

This paper analyzes, from a professional and integrated perspective, the structural shortcomings of the welfare system in supporting families with children affected by behavioral disorders and/or cognitive disabilities. Drawing from the author's direct experience as a social worker and private educator, the article highlights the economic and psychological burdens placed on families, the lack of coordination among services, and the systemic dysfunctions in care provision. Operational strategies are proposed to foster a systemic, integrated, and competent approach to educational and social vulnerability.

Keywords

children, disability, social assistance, caregivers, school inclusion, social services, Puglia

1. Introduction: Invisible Vulnerabilities and Absent Institutional Responses

In the field of social work, certain forms of fragility tend to be underestimated or ignored by institutions. A clear example is represented by families with children affected by behavioral disorders and/or cognitive disabilities. These households face a dual condition of vulnerability: on the one hand, related to the specific needs of the child; on the other, stemming from the lack of structured, integrated, and competent support from the service system.

This analysis emerges from direct experience in the dual role of social worker and private educator, aiming to reflect on systemic criticalities, collective responsibilities, and possible intervention strategies through an interdisciplinary lens.

2. The Burden on Families: An Unshared Responsibility

Families caring for children with behavioral disorders or cognitive disabilities often take on, in complete solitude, a range of educational, therapeutic, logistical, and economic responsibilities. Institutional care is frequently fragmented, inconsistent, and incapable of providing continuous and personalized responses.

The management of therapeutic and educational pathways falls entirely on the families, who also face significant economic impact. Private therapies, often essential, are not supported by an equitable and accessible healthcare system, while schools often lack the resources and competencies to ensure inclusion and educational success.

This situation leads to chronic stress, social isolation, and a risk of material and relational impoverishment for the household.

3. Professional Experiences: Informal Networks as Substitutes

Field experience shows that effective support for children and their families often comes from informal networks or external professionals, whose contribution is directly financed by the parents. Although the State formally acknowledges these needs, it fails to provide concrete and systemic support.

Many children lack effective tools to improve their academic and social functioning. If not addressed early, behavioral difficulties tend to become chronic, resulting in social and educational exclusion. Schools, if not adequately trained and supported, risk exacerbating the distress rather than alleviating it.

In individual educational work, it becomes clear that with consistent support and an empathetic relationship, even children facing severe difficulties can activate unexpected resources. However, the burden of this intervention once again falls solely on the families.

4. Systemic Dysfunction and Lack of Coordination

One of the main barriers to effective intervention lies in the fragmentation of institutional responses. Schools, social services, and healthcare providers often operate independently, without genuine interprofessional coordination. This misalignment results in inefficiency and confusion, leaving families to act as intermediaries between disconnected systems.

The social worker is frequently forced to fill institutional voids, working beyond formal duties and often without adequate tools. In a system that fails to value networking, professional competencies risk being underutilized or deactivated.

5. Operational Proposals: Towards Integrated Care

To effectively respond to the needs of families with children in complex situations of vulnerability, the following operational levers should be activated or strengthened:

- Creation of stable multidisciplinary teams to connect schools, families, and territorial services;
- Establishment of accessible or free psychological and educational support centers, including after-school hours;
- Strengthening of parenting support services, including training and listening sessions for caregivers, especially mothers;
- Promotion of continuous professional development for school staff on inclusive strategies and behavioral disorder management;
- Legal and financial recognition of the role of family caregivers, through tax benefits, subsidies, and measures for work-life balance.

6. Conclusions: Collective Responsibility and Prospects for Change

Ignoring the needs of these families means denying a fundamental right to children: the right to be accompanied on a dignified, inclusive, and personalized growth path. The service system must evolve toward integrated intervention models capable of moving beyond emergency and welfare logic to establish systemic and competent care.

Working in networks, training professionals, supporting families, and valuing active listening are essential elements for building a truly supportive educational community. Only in this way will it be possible to reverse the trend of institutional neglect and promote equity, social justice, and inclusion.

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